

Sexist Dogma and Self-Subjugation: Role of Self-Objectification and Self-Surveillance

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ABSTRACT

The focus of this research study is to find the relation between sexist exposure and its effect on self-objectification and self-surveillance which is leading to self-subjugation. The research has used data from men and women of early adulthood (N = 220) under different demographic status using questionnaire method (Ambivalent Sexism Inventory, Glick & Fiske, 2001 ; System Justification- Gender, Jost & Kay , 2005 ; Self- Objectification Questionnaire, Noll & Fredrikson, 1998 ; The Objectified Body Consciousness Scale, McKinley & Hyde, 1996) and appropriate statistical analysis – t test , ANOVA and Pearson Correlation was applied. The study found that participants in gender groups and marital status groups had no statistically significant difference in their effect on self-objectification while age groups and area of dwelling have significance as caused by varied sexist exposures. Gender has an influence on body surveillance as opposed to age, marital status and place of residence groups. Correlation Analysis revealed that there is a statistically significant relationship between Complementary sexism and body surveillance (positive correlation) & benevolent sexism and body surveillance (negative correlation) respectively. There was statistically significant difference between religious groups as determined by one way ANOVA on state body surveillance. There were few meaningful differences across the variables. The findings support that the expressions of traditional gender role stereotypes are not much relevant..

Keywords: *Self-Objectification, Self- Surveillance, Self-Subjugation, Sexism, Hostile, Benevolent.*

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INTRODUCTION

Awareness of oneself as a social object is a distinct component of being human. According to Cooley (1902/1964), “we perceive in another’s mind some thought of our appearance, manners, aims, deeds, character, friends, and so on”. Yet, scholars have also documented that taking such an external observational standpoint on the self can have significant psychological and social costs when people come to view themselves predominantly through an objectified social lens. The present research focuses on this cultural milieu that encourages people to adopt an objectified perspective on their bodies, so that eventually they view and “treat themselves as objects to be looked at and evaluated”. This process is referred to as self-objectification, and it may represent yet another way in which members of disadvantaged groups internalize harmful beliefs about themselves, thereby perpetuating their own state of disadvantage (Jost, 1995; Jost, Banaji, & Nosek, 2004).

Self-Objectification

Self-objectification is defined as the adoption of a third-person perspective on the self as opposed to a first-person perspective. An objectified body is a malleable, measureable, and controllable body. By viewing and treating themselves as sexual objects, the body becomes the site of reparative action and vigilant monitoring to manage the sexual objectification - pervasive and chronic view of the self as an object.

Whether engaged as a state or a trait, taking this external vantage point on the self is accompanied by a form of self-consciousness characterized by vigilant monitoring of the body’s outward appearance. This chronic body monitoring is referred to as self-surveillance (also referred to as body surveillance) and represents the behavioural manifestation of self-

objectification. In these types of studies, self-objectification is set to predict self-surveillance, which, in turn leads to other negative outcomes predicted by objectification theory.

Self-Surveillance

Self-surveillance refers to habitual monitoring of the body's outward appearance (McKinley & Hyde, 1996). If individuals believe their outward appearance determines how they will be valued and treated by others, vigilantly monitoring their appearance (i.e. self-surveillance) may allow them to anticipate, and thus exert some control over, how others perceive them (Calogero et al., 2011).

Research with Caucasian women has found self-surveillance to be strongly associated with self-objectification (Steer & Tiggemann, 2008; Tiggemann & Kuring, 2004; Tiggemann & Slater, 2001), and self-surveillance is theorized to, like self-objectification, also develop as a consequence of accumulated sexual objectification experiences.

Like self-objectification, self-surveillance has been linked with an array of negative consequences, including depressive symptoms, eating disorder symptoms, impaired awareness of internal bodily cues, and fewer flow states (Greenleaf, 2005; Muehlenkamp & Saris-Baglama, 2002; Tylka & Hill, 2004).

Sexism and Self-Objectification

Sexism is an insidious component of women's everyday social environments. According to an investigation of sexism using a daily diary methodology, women experience significantly more sexism than do men, reporting at least one to two sexist incidents per week (Swim, Hyers, Cohen, & Ferguson, 2001).

Although sexism occurs in a variety of ways, hostile and benevolent sexism represent two well-known forms (Glick & Fiske, 1996, 2001). Hostile sexism refers to an openly

antagonistic attitude toward women, whereas benevolent sexism refers to a subjectively positive orientation toward women (Glick et al., 2004; Eagly, Mladinic, & Otto, 1991).

Complimentary sexism is the combination of both hostile and benevolent form of sexism.

Benevolently sexist ideology may serve a dual function of legitimizing gender inequality and eliciting gendered behaviour by increasing women's self-objectification and appearance management. Thus, women may engage in self-objectification following exposure to benevolent sexism as an indirect way of bringing themselves into line with socially valued feminine ideals.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

- ▶ There is a significant cost of Self- Objectification in women's subjective well-being.
- ▶ It is also associated with greater fear and perceived risk of rape; greater hostility towards other women, greater likelihood to self-harm and stronger endorsement of cosmetic surgery and a disproportionately higher rate of mental health risks including depression and sexual dysfunction.
- ▶ The culturally prevalent sexist ideologies are conforming women to traditional gender roles.
- ▶ According to system justification theory; dominant ideologies that justify group inequality can affect the attitudes and behaviours of disadvantaged group members in ways that lead them to accept and preserve the status quo.
- ▶ Women may engage in self-objectification following exposure to benevolent sexism as an indirect way of bringing themselves into line with socially valued feminine ideals.

METHOD

AIM

The study is planned to find the relation between sexist exposure and its effect on self-objectification and self-surveillance which is leading to self-subjugation.

HYPOTHESIS

- ▶ There is no significant relationship between sexism (benevolent /hostile) and Self-Objectification leading to Self-Subjugation.
- ▶ There is no significant relationship between sexism (benevolent /hostile) on Self-Surveillance leading to Self-Subjugation.
- ▶ There is no significant gender difference on the impact of Sexism leading to Self-Objectification and Self-Surveillance.
- ▶ There is no significant age difference on the impact of Sexism leading to Self-Objectification and Self-Surveillance.
- ▶ There is no significant marital status difference on the impact of Sexism leading to Self-Objectification and Self-Surveillance.
- ▶ There is no significant difference in the area of residence (Rural/Urban) on the impact of Sexism leading to Self-Objectification and Self-Surveillance.
- ▶ There is no significant religion difference on the impact of Sexism leading to Self-Objectification and Self-Surveillance.
- ▶ There is no significant educational status difference on the impact of Sexism leading to Self-Objectification and Self-Surveillance.

SAMPLE

The sample constituted of a total of 220 individuals aged between 20 and 40 years, divided between six demographic groups : age , gender , marital status , place of residence , religion

and educational qualification. The samples were obtained from Thrissur district using convenience sampling method.

INCLUSION CRITERIA

- ▶ Males and females of Young Adulthood (20-40yrs).
- ▶ People residing in the rural and urban areas of Thrissur district.
- ▶ Believers of Hindu, Christian and Muslim community.
- ▶ People with minimum SSLC qualification.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA

- ▶ Transgender and others.
- ▶ Divorced and separated individuals.
- ▶ People with mental retardation and severe physical disability.
- ▶ People who denied consent.

PROCEDURE

Individuals under study were provided with questionnaires with brief instructions on how to fill it. They were also given assurance of confidentiality of details collected and were asked to answer as honestly as possible. Questionnaires were scored and coded.

DESCRIPTION OF TOOLS

Ambivalent Sexism Inventory (ASI)

Ambivalent Sexism Inventory (ASI) by Glick and Fiske in 1996. The ASI is a 22-item self report of sexism on which respondents indicates their level of agreement with various statements, which are placed on a 6-point Likert scale .It is composed of two sub-scales that may be independently calculated for sub-scale scores or may be averaged for an overall composite sexism score. The first sub-scale is the hostile sexism scale, which is composed of 11 items and the second sub-scale is the benevolent sexism scale, which is composed of 11 items. The Cronbach's Alpha for the ASI is 0.85. Computed test-retest reliability coefficient is 0.87.

System Justification Scale

Jost and kay (2005) presented the scale in non-sexist control condition with eight questions in total. It was a 6-point grading scale with 2 items for reverse scoring. The reliability for System Justification Scale is 0.727 and the scale has good criterion validity.

Self- Objectification Questionnaire

A modified version of the Self Objectification Questionnaire (Noll & Fredrickson, 1998) was used to measure state self objectification. Respondents were instructed to rank 10 attributes in order of their impact on their physical concept (Rank 0 – 9). The same rank could not be assigned to more than one attribute. The possible range of scores was -25 to 25, with higher scores indicating higher self-objectification. The Cronbach's Alpha for the questionnaire is 0.83. SOQ has demonstrated acceptable construct validity.

Objectified Body Consciousness Scale (OBCS)

The Surveillance scale of Objectified Body Consciousness Scale (McKinley & Hyde, 1996) was used to measure the degree to which individuals monitor their bodies as an outside observer would. Participant's rated eight items from 1 (*strongly disagree*) to 7 (*strongly disagree*). Mean item scores were calculated to provide an index of self – surveillance, with

higher scores indicating more body monitoring. The Cranach's Alpha ranged from 0.79 to 0.89 for the surveillance subscale. Additionally the measure's developers reported that it demonstrated construct, convergent and divergent validity.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Statistical Package For Social Sciences (SPSS) – 16.0 Version was used to carry out the statistical analysis. Statistical analysis including independent student's t-test, Pearson's correlation and Analysis Of Variance (ANOVA) was applied.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The study attempted to find the relation between sexist exposure and its effect on self-objectification and self-surveillance which is leading to self-subjugation. The research has used data from men and women of early adulthood (N = 220) under different demographic status: age, gender, marital status, place of residence, religion and educational qualification. The independent variable sexism had four sub-variables: Benevolent, hostile, complementary and no sexism. Dependent variables under the study were self objectification and self surveillance. There are not much systematic studies which had specifically looked into the parameters of sexist exposure.

Two sets of correlation analysis were conducted to test the relation between self objectification and sexism & self surveillance and sexism. As hypothesized there is no significant impact of sexism (benevolent /hostile/No sexism/Total) on Self-Objectification leading to Self-Subjugation. (Table 1) Sexist exposure had no effect on self objectification which denied the causal link between environmental exposure to culturally prevalent, system – justifying sexist beliefs and self objectification. The results were contradictory to the study by Rachel M Cologero, John T Jost (2010) that exposure to benevolent and complementary

forms of sexism, but not hostile or no sexism, increased state self-objectification and self-surveillance.

Table 1

The coefficient of correlation obtained between self objectification and sexism

Variable	Sexism			
	Hostile	Benevolent	No sexism	Total
Self objectification	-0.40	-0.114	0.005	-0.101

Correlation analysis to find the relation between self surveillance and sexism revealed a positive correlation between total (Complementary sexism) and self surveillance whereas a negative correlation between self surveillance and benevolent sexism. As predicted in the hypothesis there is no significant correlation between hostile and no sexism sub variables with self surveillance (Table 2). As negative correlation with benevolent sexism indicate that self surveillance is monitored by engaging in various forms of appearance management behaviors in varying degrees. Complementary sexism i.e., combination of both hostile and benevolent sexist beliefs stereotypes indicate that people would take care of how their bodies appear to others. The results were supporting studies by Rachel M Cologero, John T Jost (2010). Benevolent and complementary stereotypes are increasing individuals focus on self as an object of evaluation. We could see that individuals may have unmoved public self – consciousness and self esteem by trying to maintain their identity.

Table 2

The coefficient of correlation obtained between self surveillance and sexism

Variable	Sexism			
	Hostile	Benevolent	No sexism	Total

Self surveillance	0.120	-0.35**	0.009	0.044**
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$p < 0.05^*$

t – tests was used to determine group differences based on age , gender , marital status and place of residence. There is a significant effect of participant age on state self objectification such that age group 30-40 yrs ($M = -7.84$) of early adulthood reported higher scores than individuals of 20-30 yrs ($M = -11.09$) group (Table 3). Self objectification increases with age as they are becoming more visible to public consumption. The number and quality of people they are dealing with is significantly increased and hence is their preoccupation about being observed by others. The potential buffer or protective function that increases with age has an effect on increasing self objectification.

Table 3

The mean, SD and t-values of self objectification obtained by groups based on age

Variable	Age				t-value
	20-30yrs		30-40yrs		
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Self Objectification	-11.09	9.059	-7.84	12.201	-2.252*

$p < 0.05^*$

In contrast to most of the studies, there is no significant difference in gender on self objectification indicating that there is no fragmentation and compartmentalized views when considering the culturally prevalent sexist ideologies (Table 4). They may be striving to maintain a satisfying and pleasing appearance which may regarded in a positive sense. The specific reactance from men and women in response to sexism by self objectification has no contrast.

Table 4

The mean, SD and t-values of self objectification obtained by groups based on gender

Variable	Gender				t-value
	Men		Women		
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Self Objectification	-8.26	11.177	-10.83	10.255	1.778

Married and non-married individuals did not represent any significant difference in self objectification (Table 5) . It depicts that relationship status have no influence even though the presence of a spouse in married life was predicted to have a third person perspective effect on individuals under study. A person's relationship with significant other and its absence is associated with a tendency to show no response to self objectification.

Table 5

The mean, SD and t-values of self objectification obtained by groups based on marital status

Variable	Marital Status				t-value
	Married		Not-Married		
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Self Objectification	-10.16	10.668	-8.87	10.917	-0.887

Human settlement in rural and urban areas have an impact on their self objectification of reducing themselves to the status of "mere instruments" (Table 6). Urban area of residing have higher values ($M = -7.46$) than the rural areas ($M = -11.70$) showing the effect of urbanization , modern thinking , norms and social conflicts are making individuals more concerned about body , body parts and sexual functions from their personal identity and mental life.

Table 6

The mean, SD and t-values of self objectification obtained by groups based on place of residence

Variable	Place of residence				t-value
	Rural		Urban		
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Self Objectification	-11.70	9.232	-7.46	11.749	-2.966*

p < 0.05*

Body monitoring of the outward appearance have no significant impact on age differences (Table 7). Early adulthood is marked as a phase of transition where every individual is striving to solve identity crisis. Individuals have a positive attitude to portray oneself in a self approving way rather than to impress others. Results suggest that activating communal age stereotypes served to have no effect. Age remains no barriers for rumination and concept about the self.

Table 7

The mean, SD and t-values of self surveillance obtained by groups based on age

Variable	Age				t-value
	20-30yrs		30-40yrs		
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Body Surveillance	30.15	5.887	30.17	4.568	-0.029

There is significant difference in gender in the form of self consciousness. Males have higher values (M = 30.58) than females (M = 29.72) as they consider themselves as more functional and their bodies as more holistic (Table 8). Specific reactance from men was seen for self monitoring in the form of self presentations, expressive behaviors and non-verbal

affective displays. They are seen to closely monitor their audience in order to ensure appropriate or desired public appearances.

Table 8

The mean, SD and t-values of self surveillance obtained by groups based on gender

Variable	Gender				t-value
	Male		Female		
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Body Surveillance	30.58	4.457	29.72	6.008	1.206*

$p < 0.05^*$

Relationship status had no significant difference in the habitual appearance management in the sample under study (Table 9).

Table 9

The mean, SD and t-values of self surveillance obtained by groups based on marital status

Variable	Marital Status				t-value
	Married		Not-Married		
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Body surveillance	30.11	5.709	30.21	4.833	-0.144

Area of dwelling in a sexually objectifying cultural milieu in contrast to expectation had no impact on self surveillance (Table 10).

Table 10

The mean, SD and t-values of self surveillance obtained by groups based on place of residence

Variable	Place of residence				t-value
	Rural		Urban		
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	

Body Surveillance	30.16	5.943	30.16	4.593	-0.001
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Analysis of variance obtained between the dependent variable self objectification and groups based on religion indicated no significant difference. Religion is not a relatively powerful tool of self objectification. Certain religious teachings was expected to form biases in individuals for treating themselves as objects to be looked at and evaluated (Table 11).

Table 11

Results for ANOVA of self objectification obtained by groups based on religion

Variable	Religion	
	F	Sig
Self objectification	4.890	0.008

Educational qualification indicated no significant difference in state self objectification showing that environment have more prominence in behavior learning than acquired knowledge (Table 12)

Table 12

Results for ANOVA of self objectification obtained by groups based on education

Variable	Education	
	F	Sig
Self objectification	1.012	0.365

The frequency with which individuals monitor their physical appearance had found a significant difference in religion (Table 13). It portrays that religious dimensions advance the focus of individuals on body. Post Hoc results depicting the multiple comparisons showed significant difference between Muslim and Hindu religion. Religion and ethics are bearing mistrust and fear in the member of religious community.

Table 13

Results for ANOVA of self surveillance obtained by groups based on religion

Variable	Religion	
	F	Sig
Self surveillance	5.752	0.004*

$p < 0.05^*$

Learned knowledge proves to be not a powerful predictor for deriving significant differences in individuals on their monitoring behavior. The prominence of habitual appearance concern is dependent on environmental cues (Table 14).

Table14

Results for ANOVA of self surveillance obtained by groups based on education

Variable	Education	
	F	Sig
Self surveillance	0.874	0.419

On the whole the study indicated significant difference in certain aspects of groups based on the various demographic statuses. It is evident that the prolongation of the sexist exposure or the intensity of the effect becomes a more prominent factor.

CONCLUSION

Self objectification and self surveillance serve a critical factor for people bringing themselves into the line with social acceptance. The exposure to benevolent and complementary form of sexism is developing a form of self consciousness characterized by habitual monitoring of body's outward appearance. This contemporary westernized society has crucial implications of age and area of dwelling in viewing oneself from a third-person perspective to a first-person perspective. Gender and religious body affirmations of participants prove to be symbolic in self surveillance. The study posed several limitations to find the core hunches of self subjugation and further studies can be developed, focusing more on the present sexist ideologies.

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